

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

6th International Conference on
European Company Law & Corporate Governance

"NEW ERA IN CORPORATE GOVERNANCE:
SUSTAINABILITY AT CROSSROADS"

Zagreb, Croatia, November 28-29, 2024

University of Zagreb
Faculty of Economics & Business

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Anatoliy Kostruba
DIRECTORS AND OFFICERS (D&O) LIABILITY:
CURRENT TRENDS IN EU TORT LAW

Kostruba Anatoliy is a Ukrainian academic whose specializations include Civil Law in Eastern European countries, particularly Corporate Law, Contract Law, and Tort Law. He earned his Doctor of Laws degree in 2015 and became a Professor in 2019. He's been teaching at Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University since 2015 and is also a Professor at Vilnius University as of 2022. Kostruba Anatoliy was invited to the Supreme Court of Ukraine as a member of the Scientific Council. In 2022, he accepted the invitation to join the Vilnius University, Lithuania to teach courses to students from higher education institutions who had suspended their studies as a result of Russia's military aggression. Professor Kostruba assumed the role of a visiting professor at University of Bologna, Italy, and commencing from 2023, he is contracted as a researcher at University Paris 1 Panthéon - Sorbonne, France. Professor is an author of over 230 academic publications, including 40 articles published in Scopus (Scopus Author ID 57197823711) and Web of Science (Web of Science ResearcherID N-1070-2017) indexed journals.

ABSTRACT

The actions of a company's management bodies reflect the legal personality of the company, and their aim is to achieve business activity results and safeguard the entity's and its founders' interests. The delegation of administrative, economic and organizational powers to officials of the corporate governance body, to manage the company, establishes a fiduciary relationship between them. This fiduciary relationship between parties may lead to an increased risk of abuse. Therefore, we recommend the establishment of legal mechanisms that provide reasonable compensation to the injured party, covering the harm as a whole. Moreover, these mechanisms should aim to prevent abusive or malevolent behaviour. In addition, we suggest increasing the legal liability of officers in corporate management by implementing the exception of guilt as a condition of responsibility. The foundation of a professional's expertise in overseeing the management of a company is rooted in their unequivocal conformity to business standards. Such proficiency must empower the individual not only to avoid detrimental actions or choices but also to anticipate the possible adverse consequences stemming from their occupational pursuits.

Establishing an official's responsibility, regardless of culpability, increases the level of diligence and vigilance required of them.

KEYWORDS: corporate governance, D&O, corporate tort, corporation, shareholders, protections of rights